

ENTREPRENEURSHIP PROMOTION PROGRAMS AND WAYS OF THEIR IMPLEMENTATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article devoted to open the topic entrepreneurship promotion programs and ways of their implementation in Uzbekistan. Additionally, in the article the latest facts about developing entrepreneurship and giving opportunities to start business were noted.

Key words: *transition face, entrepreneurial ability, economic growth, ecosystem, economic diversification, tax policies, small business, support programmes.*

Starting businesses can help make the economy better and be fair for everyone. The program can help struggling countries by helping them come up with new ideas, making their economy more varied, increasing trade, and making businesses work harder to stand out. New ideas that are turned into business opportunities using technology helps the economy grow and be more productive in the long run. This IFIT report, prepared in cooperation with the Uzbekistan Brain Trust – and drawing on desk research and in depth interviews with various business, education and public sector actors – looks at Uzbekistan’s potential to build a solid entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem that could strengthen and accelerate the country’s economic transition started in recent years. Uzbekistan has historically had a commodity-based economy, and as such, its entrepreneurial ecosystem remains nascent. The success of entrepreneurship is seen as key to a wider process of economic diversification and development, and the 77% growth in the number of companies between 2016 and 2020 highlights promising increases in entrepreneurship[1]. The country ranks eighth in the world in Ease of

Starting a Business (source: WIPO 2021 Global Innovation Index). Nevertheless, limitations in access to capital markets, legal and property rights protection and deficiencies in regulation and tax policies still constrain small business growth.

Uzbekistan has an ambitious science, technology and innovation (STI) policy; initiatives like the IT-Park are a strong base to build on. The government's "Science, Technology and Innovation Plan for 2019-2021" helped to develop human capital in Uzbekistan and provided greater funding for research and development. The 2022-2026 Development Strategy, adopted following the re-election of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, listed among its goals creating conditions for entrepreneurial activity and introducing innovations into the economy. However, the fact remains that overall support is not strong enough, and there are many barriers to foreign investment and capital, especially due to weakness in the rule of law. Ultimately, this means that people in Uzbekistan typically resort to entrepreneurship out of economic necessity, rather than starting their own business due to economic opportunity. Understanding this difference is crucial for designing and implementing specific policies and support programmes. Opportunity-based companies create new markets with new products or services unknown before. They require support that goes beyond traditional companies and, if successful, they tend to have high growth and employment potential. In that regard, much of the impetus for the necessary reforms continues to lie in the hands of the government, both in providing direct support and creating a more attractive environment for business and investment.

Growth economists and economic historians agree on the importance of technological innovation for long-term economic growth and productivity gains, as well as its correlation with creating new jobs and sustainable income levels[2]. The World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO) annually ranks 133 nations in innovation intensity using a General Innovation Index (GII) through a combination of a series of innovation variables such as research and development

(R&D) expenditure, market sophistication, intellectual property (IP) protection, and human capital, among other parameters. Evidently, innovation can play a key role in advancing a country's development as demonstrated in the graph below showing a strong correlation ($R^2=0.68$) between the GII and the GDP per capita for 133 countries. Entrepreneurs can plan and execute activities that translate potential ideas into actual innovations that have a footprint on the market. Thus, supporting a healthy entrepreneurial ecosystem leads to a more creative, innovative, and dynamic economy. For this reason, governments from all over the world have developed a series of programmes to support entrepreneurship activity. However, the development of an ecosystem is a slow incremental process. It may take decades and require a significant cultural change in how society appreciates and values entrepreneurs, what they do, the benefits of their work, and the risks involved in their endeavours. As such, the sooner a country has an entrepreneurial ecosystem strategy, the better.

It is important to note, however, that not all entrepreneurship is equal. The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) and many scholars distinguish between two types of entrepreneurial opportunities:

- Necessity-based start-ups - Most small businesses are started by people to complement or replace a job or bring home a salary. Many people prefer to work for themselves or cannot find a job that satisfies their income needs. If successful, a well-run start-up can provide the entrepreneur and family with enough, or more than enough, income. Usually, these businesses are based on conventional sectors and have difficulty differentiating themselves from similarly small companies[3]. Typically, the company's founder knows the product, understands the market sector, and usually does not have high growth expectations. Some examples of these types of companies are cleaners, grocery stores, restaurants, flower shops, small consulting companies, etc. They typically receive funding from traditional bank or friends, or rely on personal savings.
- Opportunity-based start-ups - There is another category

of start-ups based on business opportunities detected by the founders where the value proposition has to do with the solution of a problem (“market pain”) in a better, more efficient, or less expensive way than the existing solutions. Initially, the founders have to iteratively discover a business model that produces a fit between the product and the identified problem. Then, the founders build a start-up around this idea. These are usually based on technologies that can bring new products or services to a large existing market, but sometimes opportunity-based companies create whole new markets with previously unknown products or services. As a result, they typically require venture capital to fund the initial investments and technical and business support that goes far beyond the needs of a traditional company. If successful, however, they tend to have high growth and technical employment potential.

All start-ups begin as micro or small enterprises, but only a small fraction of them will have the ability to scale up. As such, building a solid ecosystem for entrepreneurs and innovators needs to start with creating a business environment that allows SMEs to flourish. In Uzbekistan, small business is a driving force for economic growth and increasing GDP, and is the primary solution to acute social problems such as unemployment and poverty, especially among women and youth. ⁷ In 2005, SMEs represented 38.2% of the country’s GDP; and by 2017, it was 54.9%. They provide over 80% of all employment, over 50% of the economy’s added value and a significant increase of total investments, all of which are proxies of innovation activity. Policymakers concerned with entrepreneurship understand that a trade-off exists between entrepreneurial growth and taxes. Entrepreneurship is an activity that requires investment, consumption, and income generation to be successful. Excessive corporate income taxes, for example, reduce the incentive to start or expand a business, and capital gains taxes reduce the incentive to invest. A sound tax policy that encourages company formation and investments should be devised as a tool to

promote entrepreneurial activity. In Uzbekistan, with the adoption of the 2008 tax code (and subsequent 2020 code), the tax process has been simplified and encouraged saving and investments. Micro and small firms are subject to simplified taxation regulations replacing profit tax, VAT, property tax, land tax, and others[4]. Capital gains tax is treated as ordinary income, and it produces liability only when gains are attributed to the sale of equity. To encourage early-stage investments, especially in technology-based start-ups, capital gain taxation could be revised to differentiate early-stage investors from regular investors in established firms. Also, specific tax breaks for companies engaged in R&D or innovation activity has proven to be a very effective mechanism to encourage innovation, technology development and technology transfer in many countries. Policymakers concerned with entrepreneurship understand that a trade-off exists between entrepreneurial growth and taxes. Entrepreneurship is an activity that requires investment, consumption, and income generation to be successful.

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To conclude all given facts above, we want to highlight that Uzbekistan ranks 8th in the world in Ease of Starting a Business. This ranking is usually associated with low transaction costs for start-ups and creating the right incentives to found new companies. It shows the state's goodwill to reduce red-tape in creating new companies. Uzbekistan ranks 7th in the indicator of Graduates in Science & Technology and 28th in expenditure on education. Knowledge in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) is an essential indicator of innovation and entrepreneurial activity. Uzbekistan ranks 37th in General Infrastructure, which is one of the main pillars necessary for economic growth. Uzbekistan ranks 24th in Market Sophistication. The ease of protecting minority investors is considered a strength, and the ability to protect minority investors is a sign of goodwill to safeguard small businesses and entrepreneurs. All given facts show that doors of great opportunities are opened for everybody who wish to start or to develop their business in Uzbekistan.

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